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Research Article

ANESTHESIA MANAGEMENT IN LAPROSCOPIC RADICAL PROSTATECTOMY

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Abstract:

Objective: Laparoscopic radical prostatectomy [LRP] provides effectively results on surgical, oncological and functional in patients with localized prostate cancer. LRP that has a rapid recovery, returning to normal life activities in a short time affects the quality of life positively. Furthermore, mandatory of general anesthesia and specific patient position, long operation time and increased intra-abdominal pressure caused by the pneumoperitoneum. In our study, the aim was to present the anesthesia applied in LRP.

Material and Methods: This is a retrospective type of cross sectional study, conducted from March 2018-February 2019.

Results: Thirty-three patients were selected for the present study. Three of them, were then excluded out the study as their data was missing from records. 30 patients were enrolled in our study. Their data was collected from their file and records of anesthesia. Their ages, gender, duration of anesthesia, agents used in anesthesia, ASA, IV fluids, post-operative analgesic use, amount of bleeding and invasive interventions used on the patients were recorded. The qualitative and quantitative variables were recorded and analyzed with the help of SPSS version 21.0. The stratification of the effect modifiers was done and post stratification chi square test was applied with $p < 0.05$. The results of 30 patients study was analyzed in our study. The mean age of the cases who underwent LRP was 64.51 ± 3.76 years. Six of the patients were ASA I; 15 of them were ASA II, 9 patients were ASA III. The blood pressure monitoring of all the patients enrolled was carried out with invasive radial artery monitoring. The Intra venous fluid infusion management was being done with normal saline in 15 patients, and with normal saline plus colloid in 15 patients. None of the cases needed blood transfusion. 20 of the patients received lumbar catheter for epidural anesthesia; and 3 mg of morphine was given intraoperatively with the epidural catheter after dilution with normal saline as 15 cc. Postoperatively, epidural analgesia was given with morphine. The analgesia of 5 patients who did not give consent for epidural catheter, and 6 patients whose lumbar catheter attachment was not successful, was given IV analgesia by using morphine. The mean time taken for surgery, on the table, was 319.75 ± 89.06 minutes; and the bleeding recorded was 238.43 ± 105.64 ml. After surgery is done, all of the patients were extubated and sent to Intensive Care Unit.

Conclusion: Hemodynamic and vitals monitoring is must during high risk operations like LRP and better patient outcome and prognosis.

Keywords: Prostate Cancer, Laparoscopic Radical Prostatectomy, Oncological, Anesthesia, Pneumoperitoneum, Hemodynamic.

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INTRODUCTION:

For the localized prostate cancer, the standard treatment method is the Radical prostatectomy ; and for this procedure open, robotic and laparoscopic approach may be applied. [1] In the recent days, the approach of laparoscopic surgery is fascinating as it has less effect on pulmonary functions, small sized incision, and decreased pain post operatively. [2,3]. In patients having localized prostate cancer, the better functional and oncological results are seen with laparoscopic approach for Radical prostatectomy. Along with the prospects of fast recovery and shorter hospital stay [4,5]. In our country, recently, the procedure of Radical Prostatectomy is being done laparoscopically in a number of centers and the count is increasing [6]. On the other hand, in addition to the difficult and challenging technique of the Laparoscopic Radical Prostatectomy, the anesthesia management is also a task to be taken care of, carefully. The management of the Anesthesia is quite complex and pose challenges like compulsory general anesthesia, the specific position of the patient, the longer time of operation, and the complex things related to laparoscopy i.e. high intra-abdominal pressure created iatrogenic ally by the pneumoperitoneum. In the present study, the purpose was to present the anesthesia management applied by us during LRP surgery together with the up-to-date literature data.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study was conducted from March 2018 to February 2019. The permission from the ethical committee was taken. The informed consent from the patients was taken for the study and that of procedure. The data of the patients was taken from the anesthesia records and from the history taken from the patients. In our study, the approval from the interventional ethical committee was taken. All of the patients were administered general anesthesia with no premedication's given. During the operation, basal hemodynamic status and vitals were monitored. In all of the patients, fentanyl, rocuronium, thiopental or propofol was used administration of anesthesia after tracheal intubation. Desflurane or sevoflurane was used for maintenance of anesthesia in oxygen-air mixture. Radial artery invasive blood pressure monitoring was provided along with arterial blood

gas analysis. In order to maintain normothermia during surgery, oropharyngeal way inserted and temperature was monitored. A central venous catheter was inserted for CVP monitoring, compression stockings used to prevent DVT. The patients were positioned in Trendelenburg position with hands adducted in 20-30 degrees in the position, oropharyngeal and nasogastric intubations done. In all of the procedure, pneumoperitoneum was created with 12-15mm HG pressure carbon dioxide insufflation. The postoperative management of pain was done with epidural or IV analgesia by using morphine. The ages, ASA classifications, the agents used for induction and maintain anesthesia, duration of procedure, postoperative analgesic application, amount of bleeding, IV infusion fluids, and invasive interventions provided on the patients were recorded. The primary outcome of the present study was that investigated anesthesia management.

Bio statistical Analysis The quantitative and qualitative data was taken expressed frequency, percentages and mean, standard deviation and mode respectively. Stratification of effect modifiers was done and post stratification chi square was applied with $p < 0.05$. The data was recorded and analyzed by SPSS version 21.0.

RESULTS:

Thirty-three patients were selected for the present study. Three of them, were then excluded out the study as their data was missing from records. 30 patients were enrolled in our study. Their data was collected from their file and records of anesthesia. Their ages, gender, duration of anesthesia, agents used in anesthesia, ASA, IV fluids, post-operative analgesic use, amount of bleeding and invasive interventions used on the patients were recorded. The qualitative and quantitative variables were recorded and analyzed with the help of SPSS version 21.0. The stratification of the effect modifiers was done and post stratification chi square test was applied with $p < 0.05$. The results of 30 patients study was analyzed in our study. The mean age of the cases who underwent LRP was 64.51 ± 3.76 years. Six of the patients were ASA I; 15 of them were ASA II, 9 patients were ASA III.

The blood pressure monitoring of all the patients enrolled was carried out with invasive radial artery monitoring. The Intra venous fluid infusion management was being done with normal saline in 15 patients, and with normal saline plus colloid in 15 patients. None of the cases needed blood transfusion. 20 of the patients received lumbar catheter for epidural anesthesia; and 3 mg of morphine was given intraoperatively with the epidural catheter after dilution with normal saline as 15 cc. postoperatively, epidural analgesia was given with morphine. The analgesia of 5 patients who did not give consent for epidural catheter, and 6 patients whose lumbar catheter attachment was not successful, was given IV analgesia by using morphine. The mean time taken for surgery, on the table, was 319.75 ± 89.06 minutes; and the bleeding recorded was 238.43 ± 105.64 ml. After surgery is done, all of the patients were extubated and sent to Intensive Care Unit.

DISCUSSION:

Even the success rates of open surgical procedures are quite high yet increased perioperative blood loss, incisional infections, morbidity rates and recovery time have led the path to the newer interventions [7]. These days, LRP is thought to have advantages over open surgical intervention; and it is used as a technique that is preferred choice in certain centers [6]. General anesthesia is used for carrying out Laparoscopic Radical Prostatectomy, the patient is being positioned in Trendelenburg position; and both hands are in adducted position. Trans peritoneal approach is used with Heilbronn technique [6,8,9]. Major surgeries like LRP need multipuncture areas, steep slope, significant organ manipulation and

volumetric pneumoperitoneum. And in this way, the spontaneous breathing of patients undergoing operation becomes difficult; and resulting in complications due to regional anesthesia [10].

The general anesthesia in laparoscopic surgery, that uses a balanced anesthetic technique, is recommended. In a number of previous studies, it was reported that that intravenous induction agents like propofol, etomidate, thiopental sodium and inhalation agents like isoflurane, sevoflurane, nitrous oxide [N₂O] and desflurane, and some myorelaxants like mivacurium, atracurium, succinylcholine and vecuronium were used. The agents having shorter effects like desflurane, sevoflurane, and propofol are preferred. The reason is that propofol has advantages like having less nausea and vomiting perioperatively making it more preferable [10]. General anesthesia was given to all of patients in our study. Propofol was used in 21 cases for anesthesia induction in line with the studies done previously.

In maintenance of anesthesia, sevoflurane was used in 19 cases and desflurane in 11 cases. But in all of the cases, rocuronium was used for muscle relaxation. The used of nitrous oxide increases the volume and pressure of gases in various body cavities besides increasing the intraluminal pressure of GIT causing various complications like vomiting and bowel distension during surgery. [11]. So, we did not use nitrous oxide in our study. In comparison with the open surgical procedure, LPR poses less post-operative pain and pain is for shorter duration. [10,12]. For the management of the postoperative pain in laparoscopic surgery, local anesthesia,

NSAIDs and sometimes opioids are used [10]. It has also been reported that due to combined application of general and epidural anesthesia, the use of anesthetic and analgesic effect can be decreased. As, perioperative hemodynamic stability is achieved, metabolic and immunosuppressive activity may be depressed. These changes are necessary, reduce perioperative and post-operative mortality and morbidity. The use of both anesthesia in combination, early mobilization along with less post-operative complications can be achieved [13].

The most of blood losses in radical prostatectomy is from dorsal vein of prostate and venous sinuses. The pneumoperitoneum created, as result, reduces blood loss with the pressure and buffer effect on venous sinuses. As blood, urine and washing liquids mix, so it is difficult calculating blood losses in LPR operations [14]. In a study done by Erdoğan et al. show that the average blood loss in LRP patients as 440 ml [6]. In this study, average loss of blood was calculated to be 238.43 mL approx. NO blood transfused to any patient. In comparison with other studies, there are a few limitations in our study. The small number of samples, and secondly, lacking of data and records. A prospective type of study may give a better result.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that, the pathophysiological changes can be determined to take precautionary measures and for the diagnosis of the complications beforehand in laparoscopic prostatectomy. In our study, as the surgical intervention has high morbidity and mortality rate, hemodynamic and vitals monitoring and perioperative follow-up ought to be carried out for anesthesia management.

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